

LITERARY TEXT IN THE CONCEPT OF CULTURE

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Annotation. The article aims at researching the identification of the cultural components within a fictional text and analyzing the particular ways in which culture is represented in a text. Also, the article includes the analysis of: specifying the characteristic features of a fictional text; explaining how linguocultemes are verbalized through the linguistic units at the lexical, phraseological, and parameological levels; providing the examples of mythologemes and religiously-marked linguistic units and demonstrate how authors utilize them in fictional texts; analyzing fictional texts in order to identify how concepts are utilized by the authors, to outline the characteristic features of literary concepts on the basis of the analysis.

Key words: linguocultemes, concept, context, text, cultural meaning, cultural concept, communicative and pragmatic factors, national symbols

Introduction

Fictional stories in the context of culture are defined by the following factors: 1. the idea that a fictional English text should be regarded as a unit of culture, and only within a fictional text literary concepts can be verbalized. 2. interdisciplinary approach to the fictions towards the research that also implies communicative, pragmatic and cognitive factors.

The survey of the language itself undergoes various changes and attracts the interest of the higher number of researchers. Linguistics as a scientific discipline develops more branches that eventually evolve into independent scientific disciplines themselves. The example of such processes is the development of Cognitive Linguistics, Pragmatics, Cultural Linguistics, Computer Linguistics and Corpus Linguistics. Due to the paradigm shift that occurred in the end of the 20th century, the attention of the researchers in the field of language studies shifted towards the role of human in the development and production of language. Human cognition, human culture and human mind in general became the objects of interest for the Contemporary Linguistics.

The comparatively young disciplines are focused on the role of the human factor in the language, in contrast to the research methods of the preceding paradigm. Though the branches of Modern Linguistics study different aspects of language, the central position in their research always belongs to a human.

Methods of research: cross-cultural analysis and conceptual analysis.

In the story "Cup of tea" we can observe several features of cultural concept. It is clear that tea is culturally significant in England as a key aspect. Drinking tea is a daily, often habitual, practice, frequently referred to as a "brew" "cuppa". Also in the story the names of the places are used to reflect social condition of English people as Regent street or Bond street.

While describing Rosemary's husband, she uses the following words: She had a duck of a boy. No, not Peter-Michael. And her husband absolutely adores her.

In the story the husband's name is not Peter nor Michael. Here the names are used to reveal her husband's respect and love to her wife and reveal her character in life.

Cross-cultural analysis, as one of the tasks of our research is to identify how universal and nationally-specific cultural values are represented in fictional text. Another research

method utilized in our research is the conceptual analysis, as we are making an attempt at analyzing how cultural and literary concepts function within fictional texts. Linguoculturology, as a separate discipline, was forged by a number of researchers, such as Ashurova, Galieva, Maslova, Alefirenko, Telia, Ogneva, and many others. However, the problem of the fictional text in the context of culture still requires more thorough research, especially, in terms of literary concepts and expression of cultural values through stylistic devices in fictional texts.

- The Method of Conceptual Analysis is widely used in the analysis of literary works. The aim of this method isto interpret all the possible characteristic proprieties of the concept under analysis (its attributes, predicates, associations, figurative images, etc.).

- The Method of Association Analysis makes an attempt to find all of the possible associations of the analyzed concept in order to point out the culturally-marked constituents of the named concept.

- Cross-cultural analysis, which is based on the contrast and comparison of nationally-specific and universal properties of language units and cultural concepts (Ashurova, Galieva, 2019, p. 32).

Additionally, another methods can be used in Linguoculturology and Modern Linguistics in general:

- Diachronic method, which is based on the comparative analysis of different linguocultural units over time;

- Synchronic method, comparing linguocultural units that exist simultaneously at the same period of time;

- Structural-functional method, suggesting the division of an object of culture into several parts and the study of connection between these constituent parts.

Research Questions

The object of our analysis is a fictional text. Consequently, the story “A cup of tea” was included as the materials for our research by Katherine Mansfield.

The subject of our research is the cultural aspect of an English fictional text. In other words, the different types of linguistic units through which the culture is expressed, that is to say, linguoculturemes at different language levels and literary and linguoculturological concepts.

This human factor is topical for Linguoculturology as well. This discipline studies the interconnection between language and culture, and, as D. U. Ashurova and M. R. Galieva point out, “Linguoculturology deals with the deep level of semantics of linguistic units, and brings into correlation linguistic meanings and the concepts of universal and national cultures” (Ashurova, Galieva, 2019, p. 16). Another specific feature of Linguoculturology as a science is mentioned by V. V. Vorobyev, who claims that Linguoculturology is a scientific discipline of a synthesizing type, bordering with other human sciences, such as Culturology and Philology (Vorobyev, 2006, p. 32). Considering these observations, it is possible to state that Linguoculturology possesses an interdisciplinary nature and is closely connected with Ethnography, Cultural Anthropology, Philosophy of Culture, and Historical Culturology (Alefirenko, 2010, p. 26).

Cultural Linguistics is a linguistic discipline that interests most researchers. Being a discipline that is concerned with the representation of culture through the language, Linguoculturology focuses on the ways of reflecting culture represented in fictional texts. Linguoculturology, accordingly to its status of a scientific discipline, has its own subject matter, main issues, notions and tasks, and methods of analysis. As it has already been

mentioned, Linguoculturology is concerned with the connection between language processes and culture, which leads to the deduction that its subject matter is to study how culture is presented in a language.

Discussion is defined by the idea that a fictional text itself can be perceived as a unit of culture. In the story the names of places as Bond street to be the centre of jewellery shops and Regent street for the centre of florist's give the signs of social, cultural and entertaining life of England.

The analysis of a fictional text from linguoculturological point of view is not an unfamiliar method of analysis in Cultural Linguistics, however, it is defined by the idea that a fictional text itself can be perceived as a unit of culture. On top of that, the novelty is also characterized by the following:

1. The types of linguocultures were identified and their interlevel classification has been done;
2. The role of toponyms defining culture;
3. The peculiarity of literary concept has been revealed;
4. The role the polyfunctional nature of the concept plays in the forming of conceptosphere has been substantiated.

The list of issues includes a variety of topics related to both language and culture and it is necessary to point out the following ones: the problem of correlation, interconnection, mutual influence of language and culture, a cultural phenomenon in the language, as they are mentioned by R. G. Tirado (Tirado, 2018, 387).

According to the observations of various scientists, cultural values are the crucial constituents of culture, and they are reflected in our language in different ways. They can be described as universal concepts in which not only individuals, but also communities of people believe in. These concepts often represent something that is usually considered to be ethically good (correct) or wrong. Cultural values can be divided into several types, as mentioned by N. F. Alefirenko (2010):

- vital: life, health, living, environment;
- social: social status, profession, wealth, gender equality, tolerance;
- political: freedom, democracy, lawfulness, peace;
- religious: God, faith, sacred laws, salvation, blessing;
- moral: goodness, kindness, friendship, honour, decency;
- aesthetic: beauty, ideal, harmony, lifestyle.

Furthermore, each one of these values can be divided into:

- universal (shared by the majority of people, they usually belong to the sphere of art and morality);
- national (inherent to a specific nation and every representative of the nation, they determine the national specifics of culture);
- group values (the values a small group of people united by their age or place of living can relate to, they reflect the preferences of this very social group);
- family values (shared by the members of the family);
- individual values, representing the morals and beliefs based on the individual's perception.

The study of cultural values and their representation in language is one of the crucial tasks of Linguoculturology, as they may be reflected in a variety of ways, that is to say, through phraseological units, quotations and proverbs.

The notion of cultural concept and the concept itself is also of great importance for Linguoculturology. Modern Linguistics suggests two approaches to the problem of concept: the cognitive approach and the cultural one. The concept is generally identified as a unit or constituent part of the knowledge system, that represents knowledge structures and has cultural and linguistic value. From Linguoculturological point of view, cultural concept is defined as a unit of culture, as an image-bearing entity, which may be relevant for both an individual and a whole nation. Maslova describes a cultural concept as a name of an abstract notion, as the cultural meaning is closely connected with the linguistic meaning of a linguistic unit (Maslova, 2001, p. 48).

The problem of finding a relevant research method in Linguoculturology is also of high importance. It is known that Linguoculturology is a comparatively young scientific discipline, as the thorough research in this field launched in the second half of the previous century. Nevertheless, this academic discipline has already acquired a methodological basis which is still developing. Among the research methods used in Linguoculturology it is possible to point out the most relevant for our research:

- Historical-genetic method, concerned with the origin and development of a linguocultural unit;
- Typological method, focused on the identification of typologically relative linguocultural units in the historical-cultural process;
- Comparative-historical method, that deals with the comparison of specific linguocultural units and exploration of their distinctive features (Alefrenko, 2010, p. 29).

Cross-cultural analysis is one of the most relevant methods for our research alongside the methods of cognitive and conceptual analysis. The methodological aspect of Linguoculturology is still being developed.

The classification given by Olshansky includes several points that are not clear enough for us, especially, the ones concerning the correlation between literary and colloquial language, communicative behavior and imagery or figurative language.

Meanwhile D. U. Ashurova and M. R. Galieva suggest the following sources of linguoculturemes:

1. Phenomena and realias of everyday life;
2. Images and comparisons;
3. Myths;
4. Speech etiquette;
5. Traditions and customs;
6. Religion;
7. Litearture;
8. Superstitions and legends;
9. Historical facts, events and personalities (Ashurova, Galieva, 2019, p. 92).

Results

The results can be practically applied in the analysis of various fictional texts from linguoculturological and stylistic points of view, as well as in conducting lectures and seminars on Cultural and Text Linguistics. 1. The types of linguoculturemes were identified and their interlevel classification has been done; 2. The role of mythologemes and religiously marked units has been identified; 3. The peculiarity of literary concept has been revealed; 4. The role the polyfunctional nature of the concept plays in the forming of conceptosphere has been substantiated.

The result of the analysis of culture context through the fictional texts can suggest that English fictional texts can be regarded as units of culture. Moreover, stylistic devices can carry cultural meaning and cultural concepts utilized in fictional texts generally function similarly to literary concepts. In further prospectives, this topic can be continued in the direction of conceptual analysis of fictional texts from linguocultural viewpoint.

As a conclusion to the investigated it can be said that, Linguocultureme is a basic unit of Linguoculturology, therefore it has been and still is an object of thorough investigation, but special attention is also given to a fictional text as a phenomenon of culture, as it will be reviewed in the following section of our dissertation.

The list of used literature

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